

Skin cancer prevention screening: help or hoax?

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Abstract

Every year, in many wealthy countries, millions of Dollars, Euros, Pound etc. are poured into the pockets of dermatologists as a result of the "screening" for potential melanomas in completely healthy individuals. Is this highly expensive procedure medically justified? We come to a clear conclusion: No, it isn't.

Discussion

The U.S. Preventive Services Task Force, which advises the U.S. government on disease prevention, does not consider the benefits of universal skin cancer screening to be proven.¹

We agree with this view.

In the U.S., about 85,000 people develop a melanoma each year (0.0002% of the population) and 10,000 die from it. For most dermatologists, it is a given that all deaths could be prevented by early detection and removal of suspicious nevi, which is not to confuse with "universal screening"!

The American Academy of Dermatology estimates that U.S. dermatologists have diagnosed about 40,000 melanomas in a timely manner over the past 35 years. However, they do not say whether this was done as part of a no-cause screening or because the patient visited the doctor on his or her own initiative. Furthermore, catching melanoma in time (i.e. at a stage that can be easily treated) is not "screening", it is just the correct detection of an already existing cancer. So not a single case was prevented, at least not demonstrably.

The U.S. association notes that more than 2.5 million skin exams were performed to diagnose these melanomas. Early diagnosis of melanoma is therefore an extremely rare outcome of mass screenings.

Similar "successes" were also recorded in 2003/4 in the SCREEN study in Schleswig-Holstein (a state of the German Federation). A good 361,000 people underwent a whole-body inspection. 585 malignant melanomas were detected. Subsequent analysis showed that screening resulted in a decrease in melanoma mortality from 1.7 deaths per 100,000 population to 0.9 deaths per 100,000.

This small effect led Germany to implement skin cancer screening nationwide. Why?

Their US counterparts take a more realistic view of the situation: the benefit of screening is very, very small. If 361,000 people have to be screened to prevent 0.8 deaths, the risk of a fatal accident on the way to the doctor is probably higher in many countries. The Americans are also aware that the results of the SCREEN study were probably a statistical fluke, because after the introduction of nationwide skin cancer screening in Germany, this trend did not stabilize. Between 2008 and 2012, the number of melanoma related deaths in Schleswig-Holstein increased again. Between 2008 and 2012, the number of melanoma deaths in Schleswig-Holstein increased again.²

Now this can already be deduced from theory: a cancer as fast and aggressive growing as a melanoma actually is, can only be "caught in the act". Whoever takes a skin screening today and gets a free pass can already have a melanoma in 3 months. With this type of cancer, "screening" is dubious and lulls patients into a false sense of security. Screening only makes sense for slow-growing lesions, as is the case with colonoscopy.

However, "preventive screening" is not entirely without benefit, at least not for the dermatologists. In Western Europe, such screening costs the patient or his insurance company around 50 Euros. Thus, the previously mentioned study had a benefit of 18,000,000 Euros for the physicians' wallets.

A truly effective "screening," on the other hand, consists of three pillars:

- 1. General education, so that every citizen over the age of 14 knows the ABCD rules that are valid worldwide.*
- 2. Immediate consultation of a dermatologist (also and especially online) in case of a new or changing nevus.*
- 3. The prompt surgical removal of any new or changing nevus.*

This would reduce the number of deaths to a serious extent. Not regular screenings according to the calendar.

Conclusions

We concluded that the current evidence and the nature of melanoma as an entity is completely insufficient and incompatible to come to a positive balance of the benefits and the harms of scheduled screening visual skin examinations by a dermatologist. The money saved after ending such useless screenings should be used for awareness campaigns and trainings for the broader public, so that everyone can learn to recognize a potentially dangerous new or changing lesion.

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Ethical standards, data safety compliance and patient's rights

This article is about scientific facts. It is not reporting on a clinical trial (or anything similar) in its legal definition, especially not a prospective one. Our work was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

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